

BASICS OF THE TRAINING ACTIVITY OF A TAEKWONDO TRAINER IN A PRESCHOOL AND SECONDARY SCHOOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7903133>

Abstract. The additional education system began to develop actively in the schools of our country. This process is legally regulated, now it has an appropriate legal status, which allows the student's motivational interests to be put into practice. Schools have a wide range of extracurricular activities.

The purpose of the study was to analyze the content and essence of the teaching activity of the taekwondo coach in the additional education system in secondary schools in terms of organization and teaching methodology. It can be seen from the results that when choosing a specific training system in the taekwondo section of a general secondary school, the coach should choose the best methods of training and organization of training, taking into account the wishes of parents. 'prevents significant loss of children engaged in activities. Parents also appreciate that their children are engaged in a prestigious (Olympic) sport, and that despite taekwondo being a great fight, the existing system of protection of athletes and the high qualification of coaches (rapid development of students) lead to injuries. nothing.

Keywords: Preschool and comprehensive school, additional education, educational path, taekwondo, request forms.

ОСНОВЫ ТРЕНИРОВОЧНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ТРЕНЕРА ПО ТХЭКВОНДО В ДОШКОЛЬНОЙ И СРЕДНЕЙ ШКОЛЕ

Аннотация. Система дополнительного образования стала активно развиваться в школах нашей страны. Этот процесс законодательно урегулирован, теперь он имеет соответствующий правовой статус, что позволяет реализовать мотивационные интересы обучающегося на практике. Школы имеют широкий спектр внеклассных мероприятий.

Целью исследования явился анализ содержания и сущности педагогической деятельности тренера по тхэквондо в системе дополнительного образования в общеобразовательных школах с точки зрения организации и методики обучения. Из полученных результатов видно, что при выборе конкретной системы обучения в секции тхэквондо общеобразовательной школы тренеру следует выбирать оптимальные методы обучения и организации занятий с учетом пожеланий родителей. 'предотвращает значительную потерю детей, занимающихся деятельностью. Родители также ценят то, что их дети занимаются престижным (олимпийским) видом спорта, и что, несмотря на то, что тхэквондо является великой борьбой, существующая система защиты спортсменов и высокая квалификация тренеров (быстрое развитие учеников) приводят к травмам. ничего.

Ключевые слова: Дошкольная и общеобразовательная школа, дополнительное образование, образовательная траектория, тхэквондо, бланки заявок.

Introduction: As for the reasons for the high popularity of taekwondo in the physical education system, we believe that they can be attributed to several aspects, and one of the most important is the convenience of sports. local taekwondo groups - usually work in the same residential district where the school is located and where most of the school's students go. In addition, school schedules are generally flexible enough to provide ample opportunities for after-school, daycare, volunteer, consultative, and other educational services. The management of the learning process by a taekwondo coach in the supplementary education system can be described as unique in several aspects [5], which is mainly related to supplementary education curricula. In addition, these specific aspects are determined by the somewhat different requirements of the families of the students compared to the coaches working in the general secondary education system. At the same time, the management process of taekwondo school groups and the corresponding methods of practical training, at the same time, allow to reduce the flow of trainees and contribute greatly to the initiatives of popularizing the sport. The growing popularity, in turn, helps to improve the competitive achievements of Russian taekwondo. The rational development of the management process of Taekwondo school groups and the appropriate practical training methods allow to reduce the flow of listeners and make a great contribution to the popularization of the sport. The growing popularity, in turn, helps to improve the competitive achievements of Russian taekwondo. The rational development of the management process of Taekwondo school groups and the appropriate practical training methods allow to reduce the flow of listeners and make a great contribution to the popularization of the sport. The growing popularity, in turn, helps to improve the competitive achievements of taekwondo in Uzbekistan.

The purpose of the study was to analyze the management and practical principles of the training process of the taekwondo coach in the additional education department of the general education school system .

Research methods and structure. The research was completed in 2021-2022 in school 9 in Yunusabad district and school 142 in M. Ulugbek district in Tashkent. Both schools have taekwondo groups under the additional education department, and their activities have been very successful, with several winners of the Uzbekistan Junior and Senior Taekwondo (ITF) Championships, as well as many winners and runners-up. Interregional tournaments and Tashkent city competitions for the same age categories were held in these school groups. In addition, some of the most successful students of these school groups qualified for Tashkent's first adult taekwondo (ITF) team and won several prizes in the national championships of Uzbekistan for men and women in taekwondo.

The first phase of the study was completed in September-October 2021. We conducted a survey among the families of taekwondo players in the above schools. 110 parents of children participating in taekwondo groups participated in the survey .

The aspect of managing the educational process, including group activities, such as training schedules, material and technical support, information support, etc.; and

Practical aspects of the process, including the priorities and content of educational curricula at different stages of the educational process.

After revising the social survey forms (see results in the "Results and Discussion" section), we made adjustments to the training programs of taekwondo groups operating in science schools,

and to achieve the results, the second part of the study We tested the revised curricula at the stage. the following objectives.

The second phase of the study was completed from November 2021 to May 2022. In cooperation with the educational groups of the science schools, we corrected the educational programs for the above experimental period and redesigned the group activities on a more effective basis. The remedial initiative includes some parts of the educational and training process related to physical, technical, tactical and mental preparation aspects. In the corrective work, special attention was paid to the relative proportions of training tools in one or another training component, and also various tools, which are not traditional for taekwondo, were introduced into the training process. In order to increase children's interest in the process, several competitive and motivating tools and practices were introduced in the traditional process design of Taekwondo groups.

The third phase of the study spanned the period from September 2014 to May 2015 and included a learning experiment designed to test the revised educational programs as follows. In school 331, we formed a Control Group (NG) according to the newly revised educational curricula; and 9th grade taekwondo students formed a Study Group (TG) trained as required by traditional education and training curricula. Both groups were almost identical in age and skill levels of 9-10-year-old trainees and formally qualified for the entry level of the 2-year curriculum. Each group consisted of 20 athletes of both sexes.

The processed outcome data of the above learning experiment are presented in the following "Study Results and Discussion". It was in September 2021 that trainees were given performance evaluation tests as "taekwondo school" tests to assess basic taekwondo skills and techniques . The performance standards of the students were assessed by expert evaluations based on five main performance criteria, with each criterion evaluated on a 10-point scale. In order to ensure the appropriate quality of skill assessment exercises, independent experts from the training teams of the public organization "Uzbekistan Taekwondo Sports Federation (ITF)" and the public organization "Uzbekistan Taekwondo Sports Federation (ITF)" were invited, each of the organizations It consists of 3 experts. The group of experts included 5 first-class coaches and 1 coach who served in Uzbekistan . The performance rating tests were repeated in May 2022.

Study results and discussion. Surveys conducted among parents of children participating in elementary groups of Taekwondo schools showed that families rated children's "general motor and combined physical development (mastering the main directions of the sport)" category. assessed as the most important (13.6%) category. The second most important is "multifaceted activity in a sports group" (13.5%); And the next place in the list of priorities and almost equally important are "the quality of technical and tactical skills of taekwondo mastered in the group" (12.8%) and "the convenience of group operations for the child" (12, 5%) . .

The highest rating by families of children engaged in long- term taekwondo training is "the quality of technical and tactical skills of taekwondo acquired in the group" (18.6%), followed by "specific to the sport" important qualities. for success in taekwondo competition" (13.3%) and "general motor and combined physical development (mastering the main directions of the sport)" (12.6%).

By comparing the data of the study of the opinion of families related to different stages of the process of education and training in school taekwondo, we emphasize the following. Families of children trained in elementary groups give the highest priority to aspects of managing the group

process, as the aspects of socialization and communication at home are important for children in this age period, according to parents. Families of older children involved in advanced education and training appreciate the practical aspects of taekwondo group activities, including competitive skill acquisition levels and competitive achievements.

Table 1 below shows the results of the study group and the reference group of the basic techniques of taekwondo ("school of taekwondo").

Table 1. Test results of the Control Group (NG) and the Research Group (TG) before and after the learning experiment (n=40) of the basic techniques of Taekwondo ("Taekwondo school").

Evaluation criteria	N G	T G	The level of significance of the difference, r
<i>Before the experiment</i>			
1. Stands (training and combat)	7.0	6.8	≤ 0.05
2. Avoidance actions	6.1	5.8	≤ 0.05
3. Protective actions (contact and non-contact)	6.6	6.8	≤ 0.05
4. Hand strikes	6.8	6.6	≤ 0.05
5. Foot kicks	7.0	6.8	≤ 0.05
<i>After the experiment</i>			
1. Stands (training and combat)	8.0	8.1	≤ 0.05
2. Avoidance actions	8.0	7.8	≤ 0.05
3. Protective actions (contact and non-contact)	7.8	8.6	≥ 0.05
4. Hand strikes	7.6	8.4	≤ 0.05
5. Foot kicks	7.4	8.2	≤ 0.05

The above data indicate that N G children showed better growth in the acquisition of basic taekwondo skills compared to T G. T G's success was especially high in defensive moves, arm and leg kicks. It should be noted that the rates of testing defensive actions were insignificant ($r \geq 0.05$), while all other tests were significant ($r \leq 0.05$).

Conclusion . Before school and Surveys of families to assess their expectations for the process of Taekwondo education and training in the mummy secondary education system provide the coach with the best concepts and practical training on how to manage the process. allows you to find training methods and thereby prevent children from leaving groups. . Although taekwondo is a dangerous martial art, despite the modern defense systems, the high qualification of the training

teams and, therefore, the good growth of the trainees, the families value the sport itself as a very prestigious and Olympic sport. was determined. lowers the injury rate to an insignificant level.

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